

To What Extent Does Teacher Professional Development Predict Teacher Job Performance in Public Secondary Schools in Rongai Sub-County, Kenya?

By

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of teacher professional development (TPD) on job performance in public secondary schools in Rongai Sub-County, Nakuru County, Kenya. Anchored in Knowles' Adult Learning Theory, the study employed a convergent mixed-methods design, targeting 48 administrators, 285 teachers, 300 students, and one Sub-County Director of Education. Stratified, purposive, and systematic sampling yielded 191 participants. Data collection involved questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussions; instrument reliability was confirmed with Cronbach's Alpha ($\alpha = .796$). Quantitative data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and Pearson correlations, while qualitative data underwent thematic analysis. Results revealed low teacher participation in TPD (28%) but significant positive relationships between TPD and performance indicators: lesson preparation ($r = .45, p = .002$), clarity of explanations ($r = .50, p = .001$), and motivation ($r = .40, p = .005$). Students reported notable gains in classroom engagement (81%), while 69% of teachers perceived limited benefits, citing weak leadership support (81%), funding constraints (72%), and content irrelevance (68%). The study concludes that contextually relevant, sustained, and mentorship-driven TPD enhances teacher effectiveness and recommends localized models emphasizing peer coaching, administrative support, and NGO partnerships.

Keywords: Teacher professional development, job performance, mentorship, secondary education, Kenya

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INTRODUCTION

Teacher Professional Development (TPD) is globally recognized as a cornerstone of education reforms, improving teacher effectiveness, student achievement, and institutional performance. Across different contexts, TPD assumes varying structures, reflecting policy priorities, resource availability, and institutional needs.

In the United States, Darling-Hammond et al. (2020) argue that continuous, content-specific Professional Development (PD) is the strongest driver of improved teaching quality. Finland's educational success has been attributed to mentoring and collaborative learning communities embedded within schools (Sahlberg, 2015). In Singapore, PD is career-long and structured through professional learning cycles that integrate classroom innovation and leadership development (Lee et al., 2022). Similarly, the UK's National Professional Qualification framework ensures certification programs lead to measurable gains in teaching standards (See et al., 2020). These global experiences emphasize structured, sustained, and collaborative PD as key to teacher growth, suggesting that short, one-off workshops are insufficient.

In Sub-Saharan Africa, TPD has been promoted to improve teacher competencies amid systemic challenges. In South Africa, the Integrated Strategic Planning Framework for Teacher Education and Development (ISPFTED) and Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) have driven improvements in classroom practice, although equity issues remain (Apambilla et al., 2021). Studies in Uganda (Kyeyune, 2020) and Tanzania (Mduma & Mkulu, 2021) show PD improves instructional practice but is hindered by financial constraints and poor follow-up. In Botswana, INSET workshops enhanced subject knowledge, but teachers reported limited classroom transfer due to lack of sustained support (Tshireletso & Mphale, 2022). In Rwanda, CPD in science subjects has shown positive correlations with student achievement (Uwamahoro & Ndiwokubwayo, 2023). These findings highlight a paradox: while TPD boosts skills and knowledge, implementation barriers—especially lack of funding, weak leadership, and inadequate mentoring—limit long-term impact.

Kenya has institutionalized teacher professional development through the Teachers Service Commission (TSC), the Centre for Mathematics, Science and Technology Education in Africa (CEMASTEIA), and competency-based curriculum reforms. TSC (2021) mandates continuous PD cycles, while mentorship and coaching policies introduced in 2020 emphasize peer observation and collaborative learning. Despite these frameworks, many Kenyan teachers report limited relevance, inadequate funding, and poor leadership support (Otieno, 2023; Kosgei, 2023).

County-level studies show PD improves curriculum delivery and classroom management (Amemasor et al., 2025). Yet, gaps remain in aligning PD with teacher needs and ensuring sustainability. In Rongai Sub-County specifically, teachers report heavy workloads, limited

funding, and weak mentorship opportunities. Administrators also lack sufficient training to monitor and evaluate PD initiatives effectively (Muthuuri, 2022).

While global and regional literature affirms PD's role in enhancing performance, few studies have systematically explored the relationship between PD participation and teacher job performance in Kenyan sub-counties. Existing research is either generalized nationally or focuses on perceptions without linking PD to measurable performance outcomes. Moreover, there is limited focus on the interplay between PD, school leadership support, and systemic barriers such as funding and teacher workload.

This study therefore investigates the extent to which teacher professional development predicts teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Rongai Sub-County, Nakuru County. It examines how PD initiatives such as training workshops, mentorship programs, and professional learning communities affect lesson preparation, instructional clarity, classroom management and teacher motivation.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a convergent mixed-methods design (Creswell & Creswell, 2018), combining quantitative and qualitative approaches to provide a holistic understanding of how TPD predicts teacher job performance. It was conducted in Rongai Sub-County, Nakuru County, Kenya, and targeted 285 teachers, 48 administrators, 300 students, and one Sub-County Director of Education, giving a total population of 634 participants. From this, a sample of 191 respondents was drawn through purposive and stratified random sampling, comprising 1 Sub-County Director of Education, 15 administrators, 85 teachers, and 90 students, as summarized in Table 1. Data were

collected using questionnaires, interviews, and focus group discussions (FGDs). The instruments were validated through expert review and triangulation, while reliability was confirmed with Cronbach's Alpha of .796. Permissions were obtained prior to fieldwork, after which questionnaires were administered and interviews/FGDs conducted. Quantitative data were analyzed using SPSS version 26 through descriptive statistics and Pearson correlations, while qualitative data were subjected to thematic analysis guided by Braun and Clarke's (2019) framework.

RESULTS

Demographic Characteristics

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Category	Variable	Frequency	%
Students	Male	49	57%
	Female	36	43%
	Age 15–16	38	45%
	Age 17–18	27	32%
	Age >18	20	24%
	Form 1	19	22%
	Form 2	17	20%
	Form 3	29	34%
Form 4	20	24%	
Teachers	Male	40	54%
	Female	34	46%
	Experience <3 years	20	27%

Category	Variable	Frequency	%
	Experience 3–5 years	20	27%
	Experience 6–10 years	22	30%
	Experience >10 years	12	16%
	Bachelor's degree	69	93%
	Master's degree	5	7%

The demographic analysis of respondents revealed balanced representation. Among students, 57% were male and 43% female. Most were aged 15–16 years (45%), followed by 17–18 years (32%), and above 18 years (24%). Class distribution was relatively even, with 22% in Form One, 20% in Form Two, 34% in Form Three, and 24% in Form Four.

Teachers also reflected a balanced gender distribution (54% male, 46% female). In terms of teaching experience, 27% had less than three years, another 27% had three to five years, 30% had between six and ten years, and 16% had over ten years. A vast majority (93%) held bachelor's degrees, while 7% had master's degrees. This indicates that respondents were academically qualified and represented both novice and experienced categories.

Influence of Professional Development on Teachers' Job Performance

The study sought to establish the influence of teacher professional development on teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Rongai Sub-County. Tables 2 and 3 illustrates the results as follows:

Table 2

Student Observations of PD Impact on Teachers' Job Performance

Item	Response	Freq	%
Teachers more motivated after PD	Always	49	58%
	Sometimes	26	31%
	Never	10	12%
PD influence on learning (multiple)	Improved lesson delivery	20	24%
	Better classroom management	20	24%
	Greater engagement	28	33%
	More personalized attention	17	20%
Teachers address challenges effectively	Always	49	58%
	Sometimes	17	20%
	Never	19	22%

Table 3

Teachers' Perspective on Influence of PD on teacher Job Performance

Item	Response	Freq	%
PD improved teaching effectiveness	Agree	17	23%
	Neutral	6	8%
	Disagree	51	69%

Students' Perceptions of PD

Students generally viewed PD as beneficial to their teachers. A majority (58%) reported that teachers appeared more motivated after PD, while 31% observed occasional motivation, and only 12% saw no change. Regarding specific impacts, 33% highlighted greater classroom engagement,

24% noted improved lesson delivery, another 24% pointed to better classroom management, and 20% observed more personalized attention from teachers.

These findings suggest that PD had visible and positive effects on teachers' classroom practice, particularly in motivating teachers and engaging learners. Moreover, 58% of students affirmed that teachers addressed classroom challenges more effectively after PD, although 22% disagreed, indicating variability across schools.

Teachers' Perceptions of PD

Teachers, however, were less optimistic about the effectiveness of PD. Only 23% agreed that PD improved their teaching effectiveness, 8% were neutral, and 69% disagreed. This suggests that many teachers perceived PD as failing to address their immediate professional challenges. The gap between teacher and student perspectives indicates that while learners observe tangible benefits, teachers may judge PD against broader outcomes such as workload management or curriculum mastery, which may not shift immediately after training.

Correlation Analysis on Relationships Between PD and Job Performance

To establish the relationship between PD and job performance, the study tested the following hypothesis:

H₀: There is no statistically significant relationship between teacher professional development and teacher job performance in public secondary schools in Rongai Sub-County.

Table 4 shows the results of Pearson Correlation as follows:

Table 4

Pearson Correlation between PD and Job Performance

Variable Pair	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
PD Participation & Lesson Preparation	0.45	0.002	Moderate positive correlation; greater PD participation relates to better lesson prep.
PD Relevance & Clarity of Explanation	0.50	0.001	Moderate to strong; relevant PD enhances clarity.
Teacher Motivation & PD Support	0.40	0.005	Moderate; support influences motivation.

Correlation analysis confirmed statistically significant relationships between PD and job performance. PD participation was positively correlated with lesson preparation ($r = .45, p = .002$), demonstrating that more engaged teachers prepared better lessons. PD relevance strongly correlated with clarity of explanations ($r = .50, p = .001$), underscoring the importance of aligning PD content with classroom realities. Administrative support for PD was positively correlated with teacher motivation ($r = .40, p = .005$). These results collectively reject the null hypothesis and affirm that PD predicts teacher performance in Rongai Sub-County.

Discussion

The findings underscore the complex but significant role of PD in shaping teacher performance. Students consistently observed improvements in motivation, lesson delivery, and engagement, while teachers themselves were largely skeptical. This perception gap mirrors Guskey's (2020)

notion that teachers evaluate PD on systemic outcomes, whereas students notice incremental classroom changes.

The correlation results further affirm PD's contribution to instructional quality. Similar findings were reported in the Netherlands, where Van der Lans et al. (2021) established that structured PD enhanced lesson planning, and in Australia, where Roberts and Green (2016) observed clearer instructional delivery following PD in rural schools. The strong link between PD relevance and instructional clarity in Rongai supports Kosgei's (2023) conclusion that Kenya's mandatory online PD improved knowledge but failed to influence teaching clarity due to lack of subject focus.

Motivation was closely tied to administrative support, consistent with Desimone's (2021) review and Oduor and Rarieya's (2023) findings in Kenya, where mentorship integrated into PD boosted teacher confidence and outcomes. However, sustainability remains a challenge. Teachers reported that workshop gains often faded within months, confirming Darling-Hammond et al.'s (2020) assertion that one-off sessions rarely lead to lasting change. Similar constraints were documented in Botswana (Tshireletso & Mphale, 2022).

Comparisons with other African contexts reinforce these findings. In Uganda, Kyeyune (2020) found PD improved instructional practices but struggled with financial sustainability. In Tanzania, Mduma and Mkulu (2021) observed PD improved morale but was uneven across schools. In Rwanda, Uwamahoro and Ndiokubwayo (2023) showed that PD participation correlated positively, albeit weakly, with student outcomes. These parallels demonstrate that PD is necessary but insufficient without sustained leadership support and financial investment.

Conclusion

The study concludes that teacher professional development moderately but significantly predicts job performance in public secondary schools in Rongai Sub-County. While students consistently identified benefits such as improved motivation, engagement, and clarity, most teachers undervalued PD, highlighting a gap between perceived and actual classroom impacts. The statistical evidence confirms that PD participation, relevance, and administrative support are key predictors of performance, particularly in lesson preparation, instructional clarity, and teacher motivation. However, systemic barriers such as inadequate funding, lack of mentorship, and poor alignment of PD with teacher needs undermine its full potential.

Recommendations

The findings have important implications for policy, practice, and research. At the policy level, the Ministry of Education and the Teachers Service Commission should design localized and context-specific PD models that address the unique realities of sub-county schools. Sustained funding, supported through partnerships with county governments and NGOs, is essential to ensure continuity. Additionally, PD outcomes should be integrated into teacher appraisal systems to reinforce accountability and professional growth.

At the practice level, schools should institutionalize mentorship and coaching programs, pairing novice teachers with experienced colleagues for continuous support. Principals should also encourage professional learning communities (PLCs), where teachers collaborate, reflect, and share best practices. To sustain learning from workshops, schools need mechanisms such as peer coaching, classroom observations, and action research projects that translate training into daily practice.

Finally, future research should adopt longitudinal approaches to capture long-term PD effects on both teachers and learners. Comparative studies across counties would provide insights into regional variations, while studies on digital PD platforms could identify scalable and cost-effective models suitable for resource-constrained settings.